

Cooking recipe annotation manual

Ver 1.1

20210122

1. Purpose of this manual

This manual has been prepared to annotate where useful cooking recipes describe 6 types of useful information.

2. Legend for this manual

Blue: annotated sections

Red: non-annotated sections

Italics: sections of note

Some recipe text examples quoted in this manual may be revised to prevent the actual recipe from being identified.

3. General policy

3-1. Content to be tagged

Consider whether to tag statements relating to the cooking process, including ingredients and preparation. Not all descriptions will be tagged.

Related to cooking	<i>Coat konjak with salt and rub it in.</i> Konjak contains fiber and aids digestion.
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Do not tag statements not related to the cooking process itself.

Not related to cooking	Coat konjak with salt and rub it in. <i>Konjak contains fiber and aids digestion.</i>
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3-2. Overlapping tags on the same place

It is not a problem if tags overlap in the same place. Tags may be added in any order.

3-3. Nested tags

It is also not an issue if a section marked with one tag contains a section marked with another tag.

4. Individual tags

4-1. Substitutions' tag

4-1-1. Tag explanation

Means a substitute to taste better.

4-1-2. Sample annotation

Add a substitute tag to descriptions of substitutions.

Description of substitutions	Red pepper 8 <Substitution> * <i>Or green pepper</i> </Substitution>
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4-2. Variations' tag

4-2-1. Tag explanation

Means a way to arrange or enjoy the dish.

4-2-2. Sample annotation

Add an arrangement tag to descriptions of preferences.

Description of preference	<Variation> <i>Add pepper to taste.</i> </Variation>
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Add the arrangement tag if ingredients that are not essential are listed in the ingredients section.

Non-essential ingredients in ingredients list	<Variation> • Detroit As appropriate <i>* If available. Type of herb, characterized by its red stem and veins. If not available, rocket, corn salad, etc. may be used</i> </Variation>
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Add the arrangement tag to descriptions of cooking steps that can be understood as being intended to improve taste or make the dish look more attractive.

Steps for tasting better	Boil water in a pot, dip the pork in quickly and take it out again, then rinse it thoroughly in water.
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and reasons	<Variation> <i>Dipping the pork in hot water removes the greasy flavor.</i> </Variation> <Variation> <i>Use equal amounts of tofu refuse and mince. Using more tofu refuse gives a lighter flavor.</i> </Variation>
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Do not add the arrangement tag to descriptions with information only about substitution.

Information about substitutions	• Shaoxing rice wine 1 tablespoon <Substitution> <i>* Or Japanese rice wine</i> </Substitution>
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Do not add the arrangement tab for descriptions of the timing of cooking steps.

Timing of cooking steps	<Caution> <i>Once it has softened properly</i> </Caution>, blend it in a food processor.
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4-3. Reason tag

4-3-1. Tag explanation

Means the reason for the tool being used or the step.

4-3-2. Sample annotation

Add a reason tag when the reason for the tool being used is given.

Reason for tool being used	Turn off the heat and insert the aluminum foil and dish.<Tool> <i>Placing aluminum foil allows you to take the hot dish out safely.</i> </Tool>
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Add a reason tag when the reason for the ingredient or steps being used is given.

Other reason	<Tool> <i>If you leave the meat in its juices here, it will boil too early. Wipe it away with paper towek</i> </Tool>
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4-4. Suitable ingredient tag

4-4-1. Tag explanation

Means a suitable ingredient for the dish.

Ingredients in a relationship where one is more important or before the other are suitable ingredients; ingredients of equal importance or order are substitutes.

4-4-2. Sample annotation

Add a suitable ingredient tag if a note is written for an ingredient.

Note for ingredient	Pork belly<Suitable ingredient> <i>(Thinly sliced)</i> <\Suitable ingredient> Black pepper<Suitable ingredient> <i>(Coarsely ground)</i> <\Suitable ingredient>
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Do not add a suitable ingredient tag if the item can be deemed a single noun.

Single noun	<i>Firm</i> tofu
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Do not add a suitable ingredient tag if the item merely explains substitutes.

Explanation of substitute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shaoxing rice wine 1 tablespoon <Substitution> <i>* Or Japanese rice wine</i> </Substitution>
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Do not add a suitable ingredient tag for a cooking steps itself, such as preparation.

Step itself	1 chicken breast fillet (250 g) <i>* With skin removed.</i>
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4-5. Note tag

4-5-1. Tag explanation

Means notes about cooking.

4-5-2. Sample annotation

Add a note tag for expressions with characteristics expressing the senses, such as sight, sound, taste, or smell.

Expressing senses	Wash thoroughly <Note> <i>until white parts appear</i> <\Note> Cook on both sides <Note> <i>until brown</i> <\Note> <Note> <i>Once it has softened enough for a skewer to go in easily,</i> </Note> turn off the heat and allow it to cool.
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Add a note tag to descriptions referring to the timing for cooking steps that use sensory expressions.

Timing of steps	<Note> <i>Once it has boiled,</i> </Note> turn the heat down and steam for 8–10 minutes.
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Add a note tag to descriptions that are not necessary as steps but seem useful to reproduce the cooking or for future cooking.

Adding to steps	<Note> <i>Press down on the mushrooms with a skimmer</i> </Note> and boil for 4–5 minutes. Fill a sterilized bottle with the mushrooms and juices to <Note>about</Note> three-quarters full. <Note> <i>Hold the meat down to remove air from inside it</i> </Note> and shape it. Add the cabbage <Note> <i>gradually</i> </Note> and stir-fry it.
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Do not add a note tag to issues of written expression (that do not greatly affect the results of cooking).

Expression	Wash <i>well</i> Wash <i>quickly</i> <i>Plenty of</i> water
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Do not add a note tag to descriptions of preparations, i.e., the steps themselves.

Step itself	<i>Wash the rice and soak it in water.</i>
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Do not add a note tag to expressions showing strength in physical terms.

Strength in physical terms	<i>Low heat</i> <i>500 W</i>
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Do not add a note tag to expressions that are sensory but indicate a determined guide for the amount.

Guide	Fill the pan with just enough water <i>to cover it</i> . Fill the pan with enough water <i>to cover it</i> and place over low heat.
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4-6. Serving tag

4-6-1. Tag explanation

Means a method for serving the cooking.

4-6-2. Sample annotation

Add a serving tag to descriptions indicating steps to serve in detail, specific contents on serving showing a strong awareness of visual attractiveness, etc.

Notes on ingredients	<Serving> <i>Drain the noodles and place them in the bowl with lettuce, and cover liberally with the [chicken miso sauce] from 4.</i> </Serving>
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Do not add the serving tag to descriptions that do not give details of the serving steps.

Few details on serving steps	Pour the juice from the can in a circle and quickly stir-fry the entire contents, <i>then serve on a plate.</i> <i>Serve the pork cutlet in bite-sized pieces on a plate.</i> <i>Drain the wontons and add them gently.</i>
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